

Hydrogenation of Dimethyl Oxalate to Ethylene Glycol on Cu/SiO₂ Catalysts Prepared by a Deposition-Decomposition Method: Optimization of the Operating Conditions and Pre-reduction Procedure

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Graphical Abstract

Abstract

Cu/SiO₂ catalysts prepared by a deposition-decomposition (DD) method using ammonium hydroxide are currently among the most promising catalysts for oxalates hydrogenation to ethylene glycol (EG).

Here, a Cu/SiO₂ catalyst prepared by the DD method was pre-reduced at a) 200 - 350 °C in 100% H₂, and 2) 200°C in a 50% H₂/N₂ mixture. Then, it was tested at 200 °C, and 25 barg, while EG yields were optimized, with H₂-GHSV and H₂/DMO ratios in the ranges 1000 – 4000 h⁻¹ and 30 – 200 mol/mol. The calcined catalyst presents an XRD amorphous Cu phyllosilicate phase. After pre-reduction in pure H₂ at 200 to 250°C (T_{red}), the Cu metallic surface area increased from 6 to 12 m²/g_{cat} and slightly decreased at 350°C. Simultaneously, the silanol's band, measured by DRIFT experiments, increased with T_{red}. The highest ethylene glycol yield (91 %) was achieved after pre-reduction at 200 °C in pure hydrogen, working with an H₂-GHSV and H₂/DMO of 1050 h⁻¹ and 68 mol/mol, respectively. The catalyst was stable for more than 36 h after a 20 h induction period. Catalyst characterization results as a function of T_{red} confirm that mixed-valence copper nanoparticles favor the EG selective formation, while side reactions leading to ethanol and 1,2-butanediol are related to exposed acidic and basic sites due to decreased Cu/support interactions.

Keywords:

hydrogenation, dimethyl oxalate, ethylene glycol, FTIR, optimization, Cu/SiO₂

1. Introduction

Ethylene glycol (EG) is a bulk chemical used mainly as an anti-freezing agent, solvent, and monomer to produce polyesters. Its worldwide production capacity, mostly located in China, in 2019 was 41.8 Mt/y, with a forecast increase of 55% by 2024 [1]. However, it is still mostly produced by the hydration of oil-based ethylene oxide. The increasing demand to produce EG, the fluctuating oil market, and the need to decrease its environmental impact are pushing the research toward the *two-steps indirect synthesis of EG*, employing syngas from coal, natural gas [2–4] or biomass for the production of Dimethyl (DMO) and diethyl (DEO) oxalates and their catalytic hydrogenation to EG. Even though DEO production from syngas was industrialized in China in 2010 [5], the intrinsically safer production of DMO makes its production and hydrogenation preferable [4]. Although the Coal-to-EG route was already industrialized in China, the poor stability and selectivity of the catalysts employed for the hydrogenation of DMO still limit the potential benefits from this route [6]. The DMO hydrogenation is a two-step hydrogenation reaction where it is first hydrogenated to methyl glycolate (MG) and the latter to EG ([Scheme 1](#)).

SCHEME 1 HERE

The DMO hydrogenation was initially studied in the liquid phase, using homogenous $\text{Ru}(\text{CO})_2(\text{Ac})_2(\text{PBU})_3$ catalysts [7–11]. However, the issue of catalyst separation and the high H_2 pressure needed oriented the research toward the vapor phase hydrogenation of oxalates. The latter was mainly studied with Cu-based catalysts due to its high selectivity in the hydrogenation of esters to alcohols and inactivity for the hydrogenolysis of carbon-carbon bonds [12]. Although the use of improved Raney Cu catalysts [13] was also reported, due to the sintering-prone behaviour of Cu and its low activity, Cu is rarely used by itself [14]. The best catalyst's stability for the hydrogenation of DMO, was obtained with Cu-Cr catalysts [15]. However, due to chromium toxicity, more environmentally friendly catalysts are being developed. Among these, interesting results were reported for Cu/SiO₂ [16], bimetallic core-shell Ag-Ni/SBA-15 [17], Ag/SiO₂[18], Cu-Ni/SiO₂[19a], Cu/ZnO/Al₂O₃ [19b], Cu/TiO₂ [20], Cu/SiO₂-HZSM-5 [21], Cu/ZrO₂[16], Cu/Al₂O₃ [16] and, Hydroxyapatite-supported Cu [22]. Other strategies for improving the stability and selectivity, like the

use of monolithic Pd–Au–CuO_x/Cu-fiber catalyst with improved thermal conductivity of the support [15] and the functionalization of the Cu/SiO₂ catalysts by organo-silane compounds [3], were reported. However, Cu/SiO₂ catalysts are still the most studied ones due to the low density of acidic/basic sites on the SiO₂ support, limiting the formation of byproducts, even though stability is still an issue [12]. The deactivation of such catalysts was attributed to Cu sintering due to the weak interaction of Cu with SiO₂ [14,23] or to the poor SiO₂ thermal conductivity and generation of hotspots [15], Ostwald ripening of Cu induced by CO from MeOH dissociation [24,25] and poisoning [26], erosion of the Si support by the generation of silanes [27], pore-blocking by polymerization of methyl glycolate [28], and carbon deposition [29]. Several strategies were used to improve the stability of Cu/SiO₂ catalysts. Among these: doping with boron oxide [6,30], lanthanum oxide [23], Sn [29], ZrO₂, preparation of bimetallic catalysts like AuCu/SBA-15, the use of SiO₂ supports with nanosized pores [14]. Several preparation methods were proposed to improve the stability and selectivity of Cu/SiO₂ catalysts, like urea hydrolysis deposition precipitation [31], urea-assisted gelation [23], deposition-decomposition (DD) also known as Ammonia Evaporation [32], ammonium carbonate deposition precipitation [33] and, ionic exchange [34a]. Among these, the DD method allows obtaining an enhanced metal-support interaction, high Cu dispersion after controlled reduction [34b]. Therefore, the DD method was extensively studied for improving catalysts' stability and EG yields. More specifically, it has been optimized as a function of the temperature used during the DD procedure [35], the SiO₂ sol precursor dispersion [36], the order of addition of precursors [37], and the concentration of dextrin as a structural promoter in a modified version of the procedure [38].

Moreover, the extensive amounts of Cu⁺ on the catalytic surface of DD catalysts are reported to work synergistically with metallic Cu for the DMO hydrogenation, as supported by XPS and TPR measurements [32]. More specifically, metallic Cu is believed to be the active site for the adsorption of H₂ and hydrogenation, while Cu⁺ stabilizes methoxy and acyl intermediates and helps to polarize the C=O bond of DMO and MG [29,32]. Similar conclusions were also reached by kinetic modelling of the DMO hydrogenation on a Cu/SiO₂ catalyst prepared by the DD method, suggesting a dual-site Hougen-Watson mechanism with dissociative adsorption of both H₂ and esters and the dissociative adsorption of the DMO as the rate-determining step [39]. Therefore, a proper balance between surface Cu⁺ and Cu sites is required. However, due

to the dynamic change of the Cu oxidation state during the hydrogenation of esters [40], different views were reported regarding the optimal Cu^+/Cu ratio for improving the yield of EG [29], which can be related to the influence of the catalyst's preparation method, presence of promoters, reducing conditions [41], H_2/DMO ratio in the feed, working pressure and temperature, and aging of the catalyst. Moreover, few studies also reported the hydrogenation of diethyl oxalate to ethylene glycol as structure-sensitive [14].

Although many studies were undertaken to understand in depth the hydrogenation mechanism, even by using powerful characterization techniques, the structure of the active sites and the role of Cu^+ are still unknown. In addition, the formation of by-products like ethanol (EtOH) and 1,2-butanediol (1,2BD) by hydrodeoxygenation and Guerbet reactions [42–45a] was never analysed in depth.

However, a reasonable hypothesis to explain the better performance of Cu based catalysts prepared by DD or similar procedures and to improve the understanding of the role of Cu^+ sites can be in extensive Cu ion exchange with the hydroxyls present on the SiO_2 support [45b], which after incomplete reduction, can effectively lead to a decreased exposition of acidic and basic sites from the support, limiting by-products formation and improving EG selectivity. In agreement, the pre-reduction of the catalyst and the employed testing conditions, in terms of H_2/DMO and $\text{H}_2\text{-GHSV}$, can largely influence the obtained EG selectivity.

Here, to test this hypothesis, the EG yield of a Cu/SiO_2 catalyst prepared by deposition-decomposition (DD) method was optimized at 200°C and 25 barg, analysing the formation of EtOH and 1,2BD, by modulating the initial reduction degree of the catalyst and the effect of the H_2/DMO and $\text{H}_2\text{-GHSV}$ employed during the tests. The catalyst was pre-reduced a) in a 50% H_2/N_2 mixture at 200°C , and in 100% H_2 at b) 200°C , c) 250°C , and d) 350°C and tested at three different H_2/DMO and $\text{H}_2\text{-GHSV}$ conditions. Then, using the most favourable reducing conditions, the effect of $\text{H}_2\text{-GHSV}$ and H_2/DMO ratio was optimized in the range $1000 - 4000 \text{ h}^{-1}$ and $30 - 200 \text{ mol/mol}$, respectively. After that, the time-on-stream stability of the catalyst was tested within the optimized conditions. To test the effect of the catalyst's reduction procedure on the metallic surface area, acidic and basic sites from the support, and the initial degree of reduction of the catalyst, the same catalyst was reduced in the above-reported conditions and measured by N_2O Chemisorption, FTIR and $\text{H}_2\text{-TPR}$, respectively.

Finally, the possible structure of the active sites and Cu^+ role were rationalized to the obtained results and discussed.

2. Experimental

2.1 - Catalyst preparation

The Cu/SiO_2 catalyst was prepared by deposition-decomposition (DD) method [46]. All the chemicals were used without further purification. 15.25 g of $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Carlo Erba Reagents, 475782) was mixed with 150 ml of deionized water and 46 ml of a 25% wt. NH_4OH (Sigma-Aldrich, 30501-M, $\geq 25\%$ NH_3 basis). The resulting solution was stirred at 40 °C for 40 min. Then, 40 g of a 40 wt % colloidal SiO_2 (Alfa Aesar, 43110-A1, containing sodium as a counter-ion) were added, and the temperature was increased to 85 °C and kept constant for about 8 h. The final pH of the suspension was 6-7. The resulting suspension was separated by centrifugation and washed with 900 ml deionized water. The obtained solid was dried at 100 °C for 240 min and calcined at 450 °C (5 °C/min, 240 min).

2.2 – Catalyst Characterization

Cu loading of the prepared catalyst was estimated by atomic absorption spectroscopy analysis of the prepared catalysts. The Cu/SiO_2 catalyst was dissolved in a 47 % wt. HF solution (Sigma-Aldrich, 339261) and diluted with deionized water. A Perkin-Elmer Analyst 200 atomic absorption equipment measured the Cu concentration.

A Bruker D2 diffractometer (Bruker) recorded the x-ray diffraction pattern (XRD) of the calcined catalyst by employing the Ni-filtered $\text{Cu-}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda=1.54178 \text{ \AA}$), in the 2θ range between 10 and 90 ° with a scanning rate of 0.04 °/s and, operating at 30 kV and 10 mA.

An Autosorb IQ₃ sorption analyzer (Quantachrome), after evacuation at 300°C for 240 min, measured the N_2 physisorption isotherms of the catalyst at -196 °C. The specific surface area (S_{BET}) was calculated using the multipoint Brunauer Emmett Teller (BET) method in the range of 0.05-0.3 p/p° . The total pore volume was estimated at p/p° of 0.95. The pore size distribution was determined by the Barrett, Joyner & Halenda Method (BJH) using the N_2 desorption isotherm.

An Autochem II apparatus (Micromeritics) equipped with a TCD detector measured catalyst's temperature-programmed reduction (TPR) profiles and Cu metallic surface areas (Cu MSA).

The TPR profile of the fresh catalyst was measured on a 50 mg catalyst sample. Before the experiment, the catalyst was outgassed at 200 °C in He flow for 1 h and then cooled at room temperature. Finally, the gas flowing through the catalyst was switched to a 5% H₂/Ar mixture (40 ml/min), and the temperature increased to 900 °C (5 °C/min). Using the same conditions, the TPR profile of the catalyst pre-reduced in situ, in pure H₂, at 200 °C for 240 min (10 °C/min; H₂ GHSV 4000 h⁻¹) was investigated to get the reduction degree of the reduced catalyst.

The Cu MSA was measured after reducing the catalyst by pulse N₂O chemisorption at 90 °C [47], employing N₂ as a carrier [46]. The effect of the reduction procedure on the MSA was evaluated, reducing the catalyst: a) in pure hydrogen, at 200, 210, 250, and 350 °C; b) H₂/N₂ mixture at 200 °C; c) in 5% H₂/Ar at 350°C. To mimic the pre-reduction procedures employed during the catalytic tests, the temperature ramp, time of permanence of the catalyst at the final temperature, and the H₂-GHSV of the reducing mixture were fixed at 10 °C/min, 240 min, and 4000 h⁻¹, respectively.

A CM12 transmission electron microscope (TEM, PHILIPS, point-to-point resolution, 3Å), operating at 200 kV, imaged the catalyst. A small amount of the powdered catalyst was dispersed in 2-propanol (Sigma-Aldrich, I9516) using a sonic bath and then deposited on a Cu grid-supported holey carbon film.

A Vertex 70 FT-IR spectrometer, equipped with a mercury-cadmium-tellurium (MCT) liquid nitrogen cooled detector, and a commercial high-temperature vacuum diffused reflectance chamber with ZnSe windows, measured the diffuse reflectance infrared Fourier transform spectra (DRIFTS) of the prepared catalysts. The empty chamber was heated at 100 °C, and the instrumental background was recorded. Then, the catalyst was reduced in 100 % H₂ at 200°C or 350 °C (10 °C/min, 240 min), purged in N₂ flow, and cooled to 100 °C. Spectra were collected at 100 °C. DRIFTS spectra of the calcined sample were also recorded for comparison after degassing the sample at 200 °C under N₂ flow.

2.3 – Testing and Analysis

A PID Microactivity Effi (PID Eng. Tech / Micromeritics), equipped with two Hastelloy parallel tubular reactors (diameter: 91 mm), an HPLC pump and, two vapor-liquid separators, tested the activity of the prepared catalyst.

Typically, for each test, 0.85 g of fresh catalyst (16 – 25 mesh, 1.5 Ton; bed volume: 3 mL) were used.

Before each test, the catalyst was pre-reduced, using 1) 50% H₂/N₂ mixture and 2) in 100% H₂, with a temperature ramp of 10°C/min at a) 200, b) 250 and, c) 350 °C for 240 min (final isotherm).

After reduction, the H₂ pressure was increased at 25 barg and the temperature set to 200°C. Then a 20% wt. DMO/Methanol solution was fed to the reactor. The catalytic performance was optimized for the EG yield obtained at 200°C and 25 barg, tuning the a) H₂ concentration during the catalyst pre-reduction procedure, b) pre-reduction temperature, c) H₂ GHSV, and d) H₂/DMO (Table 1). Each catalyst was tested at least 24 – 48 h, while the catalytic performance was compared only after steady-state conditions were achieved. The stability of the catalyst was studied for 60 h after choosing the optimal conditions for maximizing the EG yield.

TABLE 1 HERE

Liquid samples were collected at room temperature by using a vapor-liquid separator at the reactor's exit. After the addition of n-heptane (internal standard), the collected samples were diluted in methanol and analyzed by using a GC-FID (TraceGC, Thermo), equipped with a split injector and an SPB-624 column (Supelco/Sigma Aldrich; code: 24255; phase: cyanopropylmethyl, phenylmethyl, polysiloxane; 30 m, 0.25 mm, 1.4 µm).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 – Characterization

3.1.1 – AAS and XRD

The Cu loading estimated by atomic absorption measurement of the prepared catalyst did not significantly differ from the designed loading during the synthesis, indicating that most of the copper precursor was successfully deposited on the SiO₂ support.

The XRD pattern of the fresh calcined catalyst ([Figure 1](#)) is in line with previously published results [33]. The XRD pattern shows mainly the presence of amorphous silica with a broad peak at 2θ of 21.04° , while the most intense peaks associated with the tenorite phase (CuO, COD, Ref. Num. 96-101-1195) are barely shown at 35.557° (1,1,1) and 38.763° (1,1,1). The latter, besides making unable the determination of the crystallite diameters of CuO_x species by the Scherrer equation, indicate that most of the Cu is present in the XRD-amorphous CuO or Cu phyllosilicate phase [33] as crystallites below 4 nm in diameter (XRD amorphous) or as a flat layer on the SiO_2 surface.

[FIGURE 1 HERE](#)

3.1.2 – N_2 Physisorption

The prepared catalyst presents type IV isotherm with an H3 hysteresis loop ([Figure 2](#)), typical of mesoporous adsorbents in the presence of macropores [48]. The BET surface area is $387.9 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$, the pore volume is 0.88 mL/g . The averaged mesopore diameter calculated by the volume pore size distribution by BJH is 16 nm. The large specific surface area of the calcined catalyst, with respect to the value reported by the manufacturer for the used colloidal silica ($200 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$), can be explained by the support's depolymerization and subsequent generation of small particles of phyllosilicate species during the DD procedure, due to the alkaline environment [49].

[FIGURE 2 HERE](#)

3.1.3 – H_2 -TPR

The H_2 -TPR profile of the fresh calcined CuO/SiO_2 catalyst presents a single maximum at 207°C ([Figure 3](#)) and was deconvoluted in four overlapping Gaussian Peaks at 203°C (P1), 219°C (P2), 222°C (P3) and a hardly visible peak at 320°C (P4). The same catalyst (Cu/SiO_2), after pre-reduction in 100% H_2 at 200°C ($10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, 240 min) presents a convoluted peak at 90°C and a rather flat peak at 326°C . Its deconvolution resulted into four Gaussian peaks. Peaks P1-P3 present maxima below the P1 peak observed for the calcined catalyst, while the P4 was similar ([Figure 3](#), Inset). The CuO

standard's H₂-TPR profile, reported as a reference, presents only a peak at 257°C (RP) which was deconvoluted into two peaks at 254 (P1) and 266°C (P2).

FIGURE 3 HERE

Peaks P1 and P2 in the reference CuO were related to the two-step reduction of CuO. Instead, in the case of the calcined CuO/SiO₂ catalyst, peaks P1 and P2 were assigned to bulk highly dispersed CuO nanoparticles [46], in agreement with the low temperature shift observed as compared with the reference CuO. The peak P3 was attributed to the presence of larger CuO particles while the peak P4 at 326°C, although observed at the sensitivity limits of the measurements and at higher temperatures than the ones reported in other papers [50], was assigned to the presence of CuO_x species in close interaction with support e.g., by its -OH moieties or Cu phyllosilicate species [41]. The small peak at 90°C observed for the reduced Cu/SiO₂ catalyst (200°C, 100% H₂, 240 min), was associated to the incomplete reduction of Cu present as highly dispersed CuO, while the small peak at 326°C was assigned to the hardly reducible Cu phyllosilicate species [41]. The total amount of oxidized species after reduction at 200°C and atmospheric pressure accounted for 10% of the total hydrogen consumed in the reduction of the calcined CuO/SiO₂ catalyst, while the peak at 326°C for less than 1%. The increased reduction degree of Cu/SiO₂ catalyst after increasing the catalyst's pre-reduction temperature within 200 and 250°C for Cu/SiO₂ catalysts and its invariance above 250°C was previously reported by Sun et. Al. by AES measurements [41]. Therefore, the H₂-TPR after pre-reducing the catalyst at 250 at 350°C was not further investigated.

3.1.4 – N₂O Chemisorption

The Cu metallic surface area (MSA), as measured by N₂O chemisorption, after pre-reduction in 100% H₂ increased with increasing the temperature of the pre-reduction treatment between 200 and 250°C, while slightly decreased at 350 °C (Figure 4). Similar Cu MSA were obtained after pre-reduction at 350 °C in 5% H₂/He and 200 °C in 100 % H₂, while it was doubled at 350°C in 100% H₂.

The observed increase of the Cu MSA after pre-reducing the catalyst in 100 % H₂ at 200-250°C was related to highly dispersed CuO nanoparticles interacting with the support, in agreement with H₂-TPR measurements and previous reports [41]. The decreased Cu MSA observed after further increasing the catalyst's pre-reduction temperature at 350°C was linked to the decreased interaction of copper with the support and consequent sintering, as also observed by TEM micrograph analysis. The similar Cu MSA obtained after pre-reducing the catalyst at 350 °C in 5% H₂/Ar and 200 °C in 100% H₂ highlights a compensation effect between the temperature and hydrogen concentration during the pre-reduction procedure.

FIGURE 4 HERE

3.1.5 – DRIFT

A large, convoluted band between 3200-3800 cm⁻¹ in the -OH stretching region, and a band at 3615 cm⁻¹ attributed to adsorbed water and OH- bound to highly dispersed of Cu ions on the support and found in the presence of Cu hydrosilicate or chrysocolla ($CuSiO_3 \cdot 2H_2O$) [49,51] were observed in the case of the calcined catalyst (Figure 5). After pre-reducing the catalyst at 200°C in 100 % H₂, while the intensity in the 3000-3300 cm⁻¹ region increased, the 3615 cm⁻¹ band did not change significantly, while a band at 3471 cm⁻¹, associated with terminal -OH SiO₂ surface slightly increased [31]. The intensity of such a band further increased after pre-reducing the catalyst at 350°C in 100 % H₂. At the same time, the bands within the 3200-3700 cm⁻¹ region decreased.

FIGURE 5 HERE

The presence of the 3615 cm⁻¹ band on the calcined catalyst and on the pre-reduced catalyst at 200°C in 100% H₂ suggests the presence of large amounts of un-reduced copper interacting with the support. The decreased intensity of the latter band after pre-reducing the catalyst at 350°C in 100% H₂ was related to the increased reduction degree of Cu and conversion of the Cu phyllosilicate phase. The increased intensity of the silanol band after pre-reducing the catalyst at 350°C in 100% H₂ was attributed to the increased availability of the support's surface, freed from the interaction with Cu and thus to its acidic/basic sites [3]. The latter is in agreement with N₂O chemisorption and

H₂-TPR measurements, indicating an increase in the Cu MSA with the catalyst's pre-reduction temperature between 200 and 250°C, and a significant amount of Cu in the oxidized state after pre-reduction at 200°C. The increased density of both Lewis acidic and basic sites as a consequence of the increasing Cu metallic surface and their relationship with the amount of formed Cu phyllosilicate, supported by FT-IR, NH₃-TPD, CO₂-TPD, and N₂O-H₂ redox titration measurements, was already reported for Cu/SiO₂ catalysts prepared by modulating the addition of precursors during the procedure [37]. Therefore, the increased silanol band after increasing the catalyst's pre-reduction temperature and the observed increase in the Cu MSA can be considered as descriptors indicating the increase of acidic and basic sites from the support.

3.1.6 – TEM

The TEM micrographs of the catalyst after pre-reduction in 100% H₂ at 200°C and 350°C are shown in [Figure 6](#). The high density of vicinal Cu nanoparticles and the low contrast of Cu on the SiO₂ surface, related to the high Cu loading and its easy oxidation (18 % wt, as measured by AAS) did not allow to estimate of the particle size distribution. After pre-reduction at 200°C ([Figure 6 a](#)), Cu nanoparticles present the formation of a high density of vicinal hemispherical nanoparticles of about 10 nm, in agreement with the formation of an amorphous surface Cu phyllosilicate phase, evidenced by XRD measurement. After pre-reducing the catalyst at 350 °C ([Figure 6 b](#)), the observed Cu nanoparticles were more spherical and aggregated. The observed morphological change of Cu nanoparticles at 350°C indicates a decreased metal-support interaction between Cu and SiO₂. In agreement with H₂-TPR, N₂O Chemisorption, and DRIFT measurements, a bimodal distribution of Cu nanoparticles is expected after pre-reducing the catalyst at 350°C in 100 % H₂.

[FIGURE 6 HERE](#)

3.2 - Catalytic performance

3.2.1 - Effect of the H₂ concentration during the catalyst pre-reduction procedure

The effect of H₂ concentration in the catalyst's pre-reduction procedure on the catalytic performance was tested by pre-reducing the catalyst at 200 °C (10°C/min, 240 min), using 1) a 50% H₂/N₂ mixture and, 2) 100% H₂. Then the catalytic performance

was tested using an H₂ GHSV of 2100 h⁻¹ and H₂/DMO of a) 94 and b) 134 mol/mol (Table 1, conditions #1-2, 14, 16).

The DMO conversion was complete for all tested conditions. The MG yield (Figure 7) was below 1% except at H₂/DMO of 94 mol/mol (7 ± 1.4 %), after reduction in 100% H₂. The EG yield was about 80% in almost all the cases, while it decreased to 70 ± 3 % after pre-reducing the catalyst in 50% H₂/N₂, operating at H₂/DMO of 134 mol/mol. The EtOH and 12-BD yields did not change significantly because of the different pre-reduction procedures. Instead, both the EtOH and 1,2-BD yields increased after increasing the H₂/DMO to 134 mol/mol. The DP yield (sum of non-analyzed reaction products) decreased after pre-reducing the catalyst in 100% H₂, while the operative H₂/DMO ratio did not significantly influence it. The best EG yield, and the lowest DP yields were obtained after pre-reducing the catalyst in 100% H₂.

FIGURE 7 HERE

The complete DMO conversion indicates that the DMO consumption rate is not affected by the H₂ concentration during pre-reduction at 200°C. The latter behavior was also observed for MG, except the case of the pre-reduction treatment in 100 % H₂ and H₂/DMO ratio of 94 mol/mol, where the MG yield slightly increases, leading to a decreased Cu^{δ+}/Cu ratio and the imbalanced H₂ partial pressure. The enhanced EG yield, using the same pre-reduction treatment after increasing the H₂/DMO ratio to 134 mol/mol, was linked to the effect of a larger amount of H₂ on the catalytic surface, increasing the MG consumption rate. The DP yields observed after pre-reducing the catalyst in 50% H₂/N₂ observed for both the analyzed H₂/DMO ratios were attributed to the decomposition of strongly chemisorbed DMO on Cu^{δ+} sites [41].

3.2.2 - Effect of the catalyst pre-reduction temperature

The effect of catalyst's pre-reduction temperature on the catalytic performance was tested by pre-reducing the catalyst in 100% H₂, at a) 200 °C, b) 250 °C, c) 350 °C (10°C/min, 240 min), using H₂ GHSV and H₂/DMO ratios, respectively, of 1) 1050 h⁻¹ - 68.4 mol/mol, 2) 2100 h⁻¹ - 94 mol/mol, 3) 2100 h⁻¹ - 134 mol/mol (Table 1, #6, 14, 16, 20-25).

Although the DMO conversion was complete in all the cases, the catalyst's pre-reduction temperature, the used H_2 GHSV, and H_2 /DMO ratios affected the reaction's product distribution (Figure 8). From the obtained results, the best EG yields (91%) were achieved after pre-reducing the catalyst at 200°C, using an H_2 /DMO and an H_2 -GHSV of 68.4 mol/mol and 1050 h^{-1} , respectively (Figure 8 b). Moreover, at all the tested H_2 -GHSV and H_2 /DMO ratios, after increasing the catalyst's pre-reduction temperature from 200°C to 350°C in 100% H_2 , the EG yield decreases significantly from 80-90 % to 58-65%, while all the byproducts yield increase, accordingly. However, such trends are far from linear and significant deviations were found after pre-reducing the catalyst at 250°C.

Such deviations, however, can be rationalized by considering the observed trends in the Cu-MSA with respect to the catalyst's pre-reduction temperature and assuming an increased influence of the testing conditions in terms of the employed H_2 /DMO and H_2 -GHSV. As previously shown in Figure 4, a very steep increase of the Cu MSA was observed after pre-reducing the catalyst in 100% H_2 between 200 and 250°C, while very subtle changes in the latter parameter were observed between 250 and 350°C. Moreover, due to the introduction of DMO in the feed, the freshly reduced Cu gradually gets partially oxidated due to the decreased reducing potential of the feed with respect to pure H_2 , used during the pre-reduction procedure. Therefore, the Cu MSA achieved after pre-reducing the catalyst at 200°C and 350°C, although slightly decreased introducing the feed, can be considered as almost invariant with respect to the used H_2 /DMO and H_2 -GHSV. After pre-reducing the catalyst at 250°C, instead, even minor variations in the reducing potential of the feed can significantly affect the Cu MSA and, consequently, as shown by FTIR analysis of the pre-reduced catalysts, the availability of acidic and basic sites from the surface and the consequent products yields.

FIGURE 8 HERE

Although similar DMO conversion and EG yields trends as a function of the catalyst's pre-reduction temperature were reported by Sun et al. and attributed to the initial reduction state of Cu and to its role in promoting the adsorption of the esters and intermediates [41], only EG selectivity data were reported. Moreover, the complete DMO conversion observed in our conditions suggests that the catalyst's pre-reduction temperature does not influence the MG generation rate (Scheme 1, step 1). On the other

hand, the increased 1,2-BD, EtOH, and DP yields after increasing the catalyst's pre-reduction temperature indicate an increase in the availability of vicinal acidic, basic, and metallic sites, leading to increased rates of hydrodeoxygenation and Guerbet reactions (steps 3 and 4, Scheme 1) [42–45]. Similar observations were also reported for the hydrogenation of ethyl acetate to ethanol, using Cu/SiO₂ catalysts as the function of Cu dispersions and the related density of Lewis acidic and basic sites, indicating an increase in the selectivity to ethane as a byproduct with increasing the Cu dispersion and the density of acidic/basic sites [37]. Therefore, it is possible to conclude that the role of Cu⁺ sites in the DMO hydrogenation to EG is not just promoting the adsorption of the esters and intermediates but also mitigating the density of acidic and basic sites vicinal to metallic Cu nanoparticles.

3.2.3 - Optimization of H₂/DMO and H₂ GHSV

After reducing the catalyst in 100% H₂ at 200°C, operating at 200 °C and 25 barg, the catalytic performance was optimized modulating the H₂ GHSV and H₂/DMO in the range 840 – 4200 h⁻¹ and 33 – 196 mol/mol, respectively (Table 1, #3 - 19).

The dimethyl oxalate (DMO) conversion (Figure 9a) was complete (98%-100%) in almost all the analyzed conditions, while it decreased to 82-92% when the H₂/DMO was below 57 mol/mol. Reaction products were distributed in three distinct H₂ GHSV – H₂/DMO zones labeled as α , β , and γ (Figure 9b-f). Operating with H₂ GHSV between 1000 – 3000 h⁻¹ and low H₂/DMO values (α zone), the MG yield was between 27 and 54% (Figure 9b), while the EG yield was between 15 and 65% (Figure 9c). Operating with H₂/DMO and H₂ GHSV values of 54 - 131 mol/mol and 1050-2100 h⁻¹ (β zone), the MG yields decreased between 0 and 7%, and EG yields between 71 and 86% were achieved. Operating at H₂/DMO > 140, within the γ zone, the EG yields decreased below 67 %. The best EG yields of about 86 % were observed at H₂ GHSV and H₂/DMO ratio of 1050 h⁻¹ and 57 - 68.4 mol/mol. The main byproducts of the reaction were, in order of importance, DP > EtOH > 1,2-BD. Byproducts yields were low operating within the α zone, intermediate in the β zone, and large within the γ zone, where the most significant byproducts yields were obtained. Large DP yields were also observed operating at H₂/DMO and H₂ GHSV of 33.2 mol/mol and 1040 h⁻¹, respectively.

FIGURE 9 HERE

The observed trends are in line with the complex reaction kinetics (Scheme 1). The catalytic hydrogenation of MG (step 2) and the over-hydrogenation of EG to EtOH (step 3) are the most critical steps to be optimized. All the analyzed steps are dependent on the H₂ partial pressure. In addition, the high H₂/DMO ratio needed for converting DMO and MG is supported by the slow chemisorption of H₂ on the Cu surface [52]. Among the analyzed byproducts, after increasing the H₂/DMO ratio, the EtOH yield increased more than 1,2-BD. The increased yields of EtOH and 1,2-BD observed at low H₂-GHSV, and high H₂/DMO can be related to a purely kinetic phenomenon. However, after reducing the catalyst at 200°C in 100 % H₂, the operating Cu MSA and density of acidic/basic sites can still change due to the different H₂/DMO related reducing potential of the feed. Therefore, the increased Cu MSA and related increase in density of acidic/basic sites because of the increased H₂/DMO could also be at the origin of the observed increase in the EtOH and 1,2-BD yields. The high DP yields achieved at low H₂-GHSV, after increasing the H₂/DMO ratio, suggest the over hydrogenation of EtOH to ethane [45] (Scheme 1, steps 3 and 5) and were explained using the previously reported hypothesis. Conversely, the high DP yields observed at 1040 h⁻¹ and H₂/DMO of 33.2 mol/mol suggest the presence of a decomposition route for DMO [45] (Scheme 1, steps 6 and 7) due to the increased Cu⁺/Cu achieved operating at low H₂/DMO ratio. In agreement with the above-reported reaction pathways, the best EG yields were achieved operating with an H₂-GHSV of 1050 h⁻¹ and H₂/DMO ratios of 57 and 68.4 mol/mol.

3.2.4 Time stability of the catalyst

The time-onstream catalyst's stability was studied for 60 h after the catalyst's pre-reduction at 200°C in 100% H₂, operating at 1050 h⁻¹ and 68.4 mol/mol, where the best EG yields were achieved (Table 1, #6).

In these conditions, while the MG yield was stable below 1%, two reaction regions were observed (Figure 10 - 12): a) an initial induction time, lasting about 20 h, and b) a steady-state region, between 20 and 60 h, in agreement with Zheng and He et al. [6,26]. During the initial induction period, both the DMO conversion and EG yield increased (Figure 10). The DMO conversion was complete and steady-state after 10 h, while the

EG yield increased from 56 % to 91 % and was constant only after 20 h. Conversely, the yields to EtOH, 1,2-BD, and DP decreased continuously during time-on-stream (Figure 11 - 12).

FIGURE 10 HERE

FIGURE 11 HERE

FIGURE 12 HERE

The observed induction period is typical for Cu/SiO₂ catalysts and is related to the slow oxidation of copper after introducing dimethyl oxalate, a mild oxidizing species, which decrease the reduction potential of the inlet stream [6,25,40]. As previously shown, the redox dynamics in Cu/SiO₂ catalysts in the hydrodeoxygenation of DMO is intimately related to the dynamic expression of acidity and basicity by the support. Therefore, the observed increase of the DMO conversion during the induction period and the decreased byproducts yield over time were related to the slow oxidation and spreading of highly dispersed Cu nanoparticles, increasing the metal-support interface, and leading to an increase of the DMO chemisorption and its hydrogenation rate to MG and EG. Such a behavior has been previously reported on Pd/Al₂O₃ catalysts after calcination [53,54] and could effectively decrease the density of vicinal metallic and acidic/basic sites and the rates of Guerbet and hydrodeoxygenation routes (**Error! Reference source not found.**). Moreover, the sites at the interface between metallic and oxidic Cu interface can be the main ones for the selective DMO and MG hydrogenation to EG. In line with the dynamic redox behavior of the Cu surface, a dependence of the Cu⁺/Cu and the density of vicinal acidic and basic sites with respect to the employed H₂/DMO ratio is expected. Therefore, the formation of byproducts is not a purely kinetic phenomenon, and the surface concentration of active sites cannot be considered invariant. It follows that it is not possible to confine the role of Cu⁺ only as a preferential site for DMO and MG chemisorption [32,55] but also as a spacer for avoiding the formation of unselective multifunctional vicinal sites. In agreement, very interesting results were reported by encapsulating Cu₂O nanoparticles in mesoporous silica, where an enhanced Cu-support interface was obtained [56].

SCHEME 2 HERE

4. Conclusions

The catalytic hydrogenation of DMO to EG was investigated in a fixed-bed reactor for the Cu/SiO₂ catalyst prepared by deposition-decomposition (DD) method using ammonium hydroxide. The prepared catalyst was tested at 200°C and 25 barg, the best catalytic performance in terms of EG yield was achieved after reducing the catalyst at 200°C in pure H₂. This treatment leads to an optimal tradeoff between the achieved metallic surface area of copper and the concentration of vicinal acidic/basic hydroxyls and metallic sites, minimizing the formation of over-hydrogenated byproducts. The experimental conditions were further optimized with respect to the H₂ GHSV and H₂/DMO ratio, operating in the range 1000-4000 h⁻¹ and 40-200 mol/mol, while keeping the operating temperature and pressure fixed at 200 °C and 25 barg, respectively. The obtained results indicate an optimum catalyst performance with a GHSV of 1050 h⁻¹ and H₂/DMO of 68. A 92 % yield was achieved operating in optimized conditions for a time-on-stream of 50 h. Testing the catalyst time-on-stream stability, the conversion and ethylene glycol productivity increased during the first 20 h and were stable for the remaining time. Conversely, a decreasing yield of over hydrogenated byproducts was found over the investigated time-on-stream, which was related to the slow oxidation of Cu at the metal-support interface. The presence of Cu⁺ sites on the borders of Cu nanoparticles at the metal-support interface was shown to be the key optimization factor for improving dimethyl oxalate conversion, increasing the EG yield and decreasing the yield of over hydrogenated byproducts.

Moreover, increasing the concentration of unreduced Cu can lead to an insufficient surface concentration of H₂ and DMO decomposition, as shown by comparing the EG and DP yields after pre-reducing the catalyst at 200 °C in 50% H₂/N₂ and 100% H₂. In comparison, the Cu over-reduction at temperature higher than 200°C leads to vicinal metallic and acidic/basic sites.

The present results offer a new and cost-effective way for the optimization of the catalytic performance of Cu/SiO₂ catalysts, potentially improving their durability and opening new ways of improving the development of new catalysts and their industrialization.

Declaration of Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Figures, Tables, and Schemes Captions

- Scheme 1. Main reaction pathways.
- Scheme 2. Dynamic state of the catalytic surface.
- Figure 1 XRD pattern of the Fresh Calcined Catalyst
- Figure 2 N₂ adsorption isotherm at 77 K of the calcined catalyst.
- Figure 3 TPR of the a) CuO reference standard, b) CuO/SiO₂ - fresh calcined catalyst, c) Cu/SiO₂ - fresh catalyst after reduction at 200°C in 100% H₂ within the same conditions used for the tests (5% H₂/Ar, 3 °C/min, 240 min, 1.013 bar). In the inset the magnified superposition of the measured TPR spectra of the reduced Cu/SiO₂ catalyst and the CuO/SiO₂.
- Figure 4 Cu MSA measured by N₂O pulse chemisorption at 90°C after reduction a) in pure H₂ and in b) 5% H₂/Ar mixture at the temperature indicated in the figure (the temperature ramp, the isothermal reduction step, and the pressure of H₂ were kept constant during the reduction, respectively at 10 °C/min, 240 min, 1.013 bar).
- Figure 5 DRIFTS of the fresh catalyst: as prepared (calcined) and after pre-reduction in 100% H₂ at 200 and 350 °C (ramp: 10 °C/min, isothermal time at the final temperature: 240 min, 1.013 bar).
- Figure 6 TEM micrographs of the catalyst after reduction in pure H₂ a) at 200°C and b) at 350 °C (the temperature ramp, the isothermal reduction step, and the pressure of H₂ were kept constant during the reduction, respectively at 10 °C/min, 240 min, 1.013 bar).
- Figure 7 Effect of the H₂ concentration in the catalyst reduction treatment on the product distribution operating with H₂/DMO of 94 and 134 mol/mol (Catalyst's pre-reduction at 200 °C, 10°C/min for 240 min in 100% H₂ or 50% H₂/N₂ – Testing conditions: 200 °C, 25 barg, H₂ GHSV 2100 h⁻¹).
- Figure 8 Yields of a) MG, b) EG, c) EtOH, d) 1,2-BD and e) DP at 200°C and 25 barg at three different H₂ GHSV – H₂/DMO conditions after reducing the catalyst in pure H₂ at 200, 250, and 350°C in pure H₂ (ramp: 10°C/min; final isothermal stage: 240 min, 1.013 bar).
- Figure 9 Effect of H₂ GHSV (h⁻¹) and H₂/DMO (mol/mol) on the a) DMO Conversion and Yields of b) MG, c) EG, d) EtOH, e) 1,2-BD, and f) DP

products (operating conditions: 200°C, 25 barg; catalyst pre-reduced at 200°C in H₂ at 200 °C, 10°C/min, 1.013 bar for 240 min; color scales and points size are proportional to conversion and yields).

- Figure 10 Stability test: Effect of time (h) on DMO conversion and EG selectivity at 200 °C, 25 barg (H₂/DMO 68.3 mol/mol; GHSV 1050 h⁻¹; catalyst pre-reduced at 200°C in H₂ at 200 °C, 10°C/min, 1.013 bar for 240 min; – interpolating lines: $y = p \cdot (1 - e^{-kt})$; - - 95% C.I.).
- Figure 11 TEM Stability test: Effect of time (h) on EtOH and 12-BD at 200 °C, 25 barg (H₂/DMO 68.3 mol/mol; GHSV 1050 h⁻¹; catalyst pre-reduced at 200°C in H₂ at 200 °C, 10°C/min, 1.013 bar for 240 min; – interpolating lines: $y = p \cdot (-1 + e^{-kt})$; - - 95% C.I.).
- Figure 12 Stability test: Effect of time (h) on HDP at 200 °C, 25 barg (H₂/DMO 68.3 mol/mol; GHSV 1050 h⁻¹; catalyst pre-reduced at 200°C in H₂ at 200 °C, 10°C/min, 1.013 bar for 240 min; – interpolating line: $y = p \cdot (-1 + e^{-kt})$; - - 95% C.I.)

Table 1. Operating Conditions (Catalyst pre-reduced using a temperature ramp and isothermal time of 10°C/min and 240 min, respectively; the amount of catalyst, testing temperature, and pressure fixed at 0.85 g, 200°C, and 25 barg, respectively).

#	Reducing Mixture	Catalyst Pre-Reduction T (°C)	H ₂ GHSV (h ⁻¹)	H ₂ /DMO (mol/mol)		
1	50% H ₂ /N ₂	200	2100	94		
2				134		
3				840	131.3	
4				1040	33.2	
5				1050	57	
6					68.4	
7					1080	168.8
8					1260	196.9
9					1460	65.2
10					47.8	
11	100% H ₂	200	1500	81.4		
12				94		
13				67		
14				2100	94	
15					114	
16					134	
17					2940	131.3
18					3000	94
19				4200	131.3	
20					1050	68.4
21	250	2100	94			
22			134			
23		1050	68.4			
24	350	2100	94			
25			134			

Graphical Abstract

Gray Scale in the Print

SCHEME 1

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FIGURE 1

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FIGURE 2

Color in the Print

FIGURE 3

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FIGURE 4

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FIGURE 5

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FIGURE 6

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FIGURE 7

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FIGURE 8

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as Full Page Size

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FIGURE 9

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FIGURE 10

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FIGURE 11

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FIGURE 12

Cu Phyllosilicate

CuO

Metallic Cu nanoparticle

SiO₂

DMO Decomposition
MG polymerization

EG

Hydrodeoxygenation
Guerbet

Color in the Print

-Vicinal Cu⁰ &
Acidic & Basic sites

-Vicinal Cu⁰ &
Acidic & Basic sites

-Vicinal Cu⁰
& Acidic & Basic sites

Catalyst's
pre-reduction

T_r

$p_{H_2,r}$

$\frac{H_2}{DMO}$

Testing

Time on-stream (h)

$$f \left(T_r, p_{H_2,r}, \frac{H_2}{DMO}, T_{testing}, P_{Testing}, \dots \right)$$

SCHEME 2